

Effect of MgF_2 addition on the mechanical properties of hydroxyapatite synthesized via powder metallurgy

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ABSTRACT

Hydroxyapatite, a type of bioceramics, is mainly used as an implant for hard tissues due to its similarity to the structure of hard tissues. The aim of this study is to improve the mechanical properties of hydroxyapatite for biological uses. For this purpose the effect of magnesium fluoride (MgF_2) addition with different weight percentages (0, 5, 7.5 and 10 wt. %) on the mechanical properties of pure hydroxyapatite sintered at various temperatures (900, 1000 and 1100 °C) was investigated. XRD analysis was performed to study the decomposition of hydroxyapatite and the transformed phases. The density, Vickers microhardness and fracture toughness of the specimens were measured. The SEM analysis was performed to investigate the microstructure of samples. The results showed that the decomposition of hydroxyapatite to tri-calcium phosphate (TCP) decreased with increasing MgF_2 . Also, an increment in density and mechanical properties of the specimens were observed with increasing the amount of hydroxyapatite. The fracture toughness of sintered pure hydroxyapatite increased from 2.3 to 1.3 $MPa.m^{1/2}$. The specimen containing 10 wt. % MgF_2 sintered at 1100 °C showed the best mechanical properties.

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1. Introduction

Hydroxyapatite (HA), with the chemical composition of $Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2$ [1, 2], due to its similarity to inorganic sections of bone and biocompatibility, is an important material in bone replacement as well as implants for hard tissues. HA is used in various fields such as biomedical applications [3-8]. Due to poor mechanical properties of HA, especially low flexural strength and fracture toughness, its uses are limited to applications with no mechanical stress or low stress [9-14]. Therefore, efforts have been made to improve the mechanical properties of HA-based implants [15-24].

During the sintering process of HA, it decomposes to TCP or tetra-calcium phosphate phases (reactions (1) and (2)) [10, 25].

These decomposition reactions may negatively affect the density and consequently the mechanical properties of HA, which is due to the formation of secondary phases and production of H_2O . Also, the formed secondary phases increase the tendency for crack growth and biodeg-

radation of HA ceramics. Meanwhile, TCP formation due to its high solubility, reduces the properties of HA composites [26].

Moreover, the addition of additives during the sintering process leads to the prevention of the HA to TCP degradation, as well as improvement in its mechanical properties. Several researches have been performed to investigate the effect of various additives such as MgF_2 [9, 10, 13], AlF_3 [27], NH_4F [28], MgO [29], $AgNO_3$ [30], $LiNO_3$ [26], CaF_2 [31] and etc. [32-36]. On the other hand, recently, attentions have been paid to the effect of different parameters e.g. temperature on HA properties [3, 37, 38]. In this regard, fluoride ion is known to be an important additive for HA. This is due to the substitution (or doping) of the F^- with OH^- presented in HA, which prevents the degradation of the HA or reduces the level of the decomposition to TCP. This results in the improvement of the mechanical properties. On the other hand, with entrance of F^- into the HA network, fluorapatite is formed which has higher thermal and chemical stability than that of HA that also prevents tooth and bone decay [9, 10, 13, 25, 39].

Mechanical alloying is known to have various advantages such as low time consumption [40-45], facility of process, and effective prop-

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Fig. 1. SEM image of (a) HA powder and (b) primary MgF₂ powder.

Fig. 2. X-ray diffraction spectra for specimens containing different percentages of MgF₂ sintered for 1 hour at (a) 900 °C, (b) 1000 °C, and (c) 1100 °C.

erties [46] that can be a good candidate to produce HA [47]. Although several research has been conducted to study the effect of adding MgF₂ to HA and its composites, further studies are required to investigate the effect MgF₂ addition to HA. Therefore, the aim of this study is to elucidate the effect of adding different amounts of the MgF₂ at different sintering temperatures on the mechanical properties and stability of HA as well as determining the optimum percentage of MgF₂ for preparing a biomaterial with desirable properties. For this purpose, MgF₂ with weight percentages of 5, 7.5 and 10 were added to HA and sintered at 900 to 1100 °C. Finally, the density, microstructure, hardness and fracture toughness of the specimens were evaluated.

2. Materials and methods

High purity HA powder (99.99%), the product of Aldrich Company, and MgF₂ powder of 97% purity from Analytical Fluka Company were provided. Fig. 1 shows the image of the purchased primary powders. Different weight percentages (5, 7.5 and 10 wt. %) of MgF₂ were added to HA. The mixtures containing HA and various amounts of MgF₂ were milled for 24 hours using alumina pellets. After the milling process, the mixtures were subjected to the cold isostatic press at 130 MPa. Then, they were sintered at temperatures of 900 to 1100 °C under airflow for 1 h without pressure.

The density of specimens was measured by the Archimedes method. The formed phases were evaluated after the sintering process using XRD analysis (INEL Equinox 3000). The test was performed by a diffractom-

etry method using Cu-K_α irradiation ($\lambda=1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) under a voltage of 40 kV and a current of 30 mA. The specimens were evaluated at angles between 2 θ of 15 and 65 degrees. In order to investigate the microstructure, the sections of the specimens were polished using diamond paste and etched. Finally, the microstructure of the specimens was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, AIS 2300-seron Tech) with an accelerating voltage of 20 kV. The hardness of the specimens was measured by Vickers microhardness test method (MHV1000Z), which was performed under 200 g load on the polished surfaces of the specimens for 10 sec. The values of fracture toughness (K_{IC}) were calculated using the results obtained from the microhardness test based on Eq. (3) [48].

$$K_{IC} = 0.016 \left(\frac{E}{H_V} \right)^{0.5} \left(\frac{P}{C^{1.5}} \right) \quad (3)$$

Here, HV is Vickers hardness (GPa), P is the applied force (N), E is the modulus of elasticity (GPa) and C is the crack length (m). The crack length was measured immediately by a calibrated optical microscope.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Phase Analysis

XRD analysis was used to evaluate the degradation of HA as well as determining the formed phases. Fig. 2 shows the X-ray diffraction for different percentages of MgF₂ at different sintering times.

Fig. 2 shows that HA and TCP are the main phases in the structure,

Fig. 3. Density variations of the specimens as percentage of MgF₂ at different temperatures of sintering.

while MgF₂ does not exist in the structure after the sintering process. This indicates that the decomposition of HA to TCP occurs due to sintering process.

The XRD spectra depicts that by the addition of MgF₂ to HA, the fluorapatite phase is also formed in the structure and after the sintering process, the phases of HA, TCP, fluorapatite and MgO are presented in the structure. The formation of the fluorapatite phase is because of F⁻ substitution instead of OH⁻ ions in the HA structure according to reaction (4). $Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2 + MgF_2 \rightarrow Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6F_2 + MgO + H_2O$ (4)

Also, in order to evaluate the degradation rate of HA, it is necessary to check the intensity of HA and TCP peaks. To determine the HA decomposition into TCP, the relative values of the phases can be determined from the most extreme HA and TCP peaks. In fact, it is assumed that the concentrations of the HA and TCP phases are proportional to the height of their peaks in the mixture [10]. The rate of TCP formation in structures containing HA and TCP can be calculated using Eq. (5) [32].

$$\text{the fraction of decomposed HA} = \frac{I_{TCP}}{I_{TCP} + I_{HA}} \quad (5)$$

where I_{TCP} is the peak intensity of the plane (0210) of the TCP phase and I_{HA} is the peak intensity of the plane (211) of HA. Using this equation, the percentage of HA decomposed into calcium phosphate can be determined. Clearly, the greater the value obtained from this relationship, the greater the decomposition. These values were calculated for different specimens and listed in Table 1.

According to calculations based on Eq. 5, the most appropriate sintering temperature for 5 and 7.5 wt. % MgF₂ was 900 °C, while for the specimen with 10 wt.% MgF₂, sintering temperature of 1100 °C was suitable, in which, the lowest decomposition of 1.82 was observed. It should be noted that as the sintering temperature increased, the decomposition of pure HA significantly increased. The main reason for the decrease in the amount of degradation in the presence of fluorides is decomposition of MgF₂. As a result of this decomposition, F⁻ is released and replaced in the HA structure by the OH⁻ [9]. As a result of MgF₂ decomposition and reaction (4), a more stable phase of fluorapatite is formed and thus the decomposition of HA to TCP is reduced. Fluoride ions enhance the stability of the HA crystalline structure [13], and HA doped with F (fluorapatite) is more resistant to decomposition during sintering at high temperature than pure HA. According to Table 1, the higher the percentage of MgF₂ in the structure, the lower the degradation of HA to TCP and the more stable HA. As can be seen, the specimen containing 10 wt. % MgF₂ has only ~2 % of the decomposed-HA to TCP, and hence, HA stability is significantly increased. The main reason for this could be higher F⁻ ions due to presence of higher MgF₂ content presented in the HA structure and consequently the reaction (4) occurs more, and higher fluorapatite is formed, thus the decomposition of HA to TCP is more prevented.

It should be noted that for samples from 7.5 to 10 wt. %, the degradation is increased. The reason for the negative effect of adding more than specific amount of MgF₂ on the stability of HA is that the excess MgF₂ does not participate in the formation of fluorapatite and is not visible in the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern because of its low content. This

Fig. 4. SEM images of sintered specimens at 900 °C: (a) 0 wt. % MgF₂; (b) 5 wt. % MgF₂; (c) 7.5 wt. % MgF₂; (d) 10 wt. % MgF₂.

excess MgF₂ forms eutectic melt at the reaction temperatures with HA or TCP. In fact, the relative coarsening of the grains and porosities with the addition of higher amounts of MgF₂ indicates the possibility of eutectic melt formation. This has been observed in other works [13, 49].

3.2. Density

The density values obtained for the specimens at different temperatures are presented in Fig. 3. Accordingly, the MgF₂-free specimen has the lowest density compared to other specimens. It can be noted that in the presence of MgF₂, the phase decomposition of HA into secondary phases i.e. TCP is reduced that leads to higher density. The reason for the higher density due to lower HA degradation is the production of H₂O by decomposition of HA to TCP (reactions (1) and (2)). The produced H₂O results in porosity. On the other hand, by decreasing the amount of HA decomposition in the presence of MgF₂, less H₂O and porosity in the structure is produced and hence the density increases [9, 10]. It was also observed that by increasing the MgF₂ content, the density increases. According to Table 1, HA decomposition decreases with an increasing percentage of MgF₂. Additionally, the reduction of HA decomposition during sintering, reduces the amount of H₂O formed by HA decomposition and thus reduces the porosity of the sintered specimens. As a result, when HA decomposition becomes lower, the removal of porosity in the final sintering stages becomes easier, which results in a highly dense structure [10].

The TCP phase resulted from the decomposition of HA has a lower density. As a result, specimens with higher TCP phase have lower density [13]. Also, substitution of OH⁻ with F⁻ (reaction (4)) results in H₂O production. Replacement occurs below sintering temperature (below 1100 °C). The H₂O produced in this reaction vaporizes and discharges from the powder mixture and fluorapatite is formed (Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆F₂) [9].

Table 1.
Percentage of HA decomposed to TCP

Percentage of decomposed HA (%)	MgF ₂ (wt. %)
86.31	0
58.97	5
33.24	7.5
1.82	10

Fig. 5. SEM images of sintered specimens at 1000 °C: (a) 0 wt.% MgF₂; b) 5 wt.% MgF₂; c) 7.5 wt.% MgF₂; d) 10 wt.% MgF₂.

Fig. 7. Micro hardness values by weight percent of MgF₂ at different temperatures.

At two temperatures of 900 °C and 1000 °C, the density decreased with increasing MgF₂ from 7.5 to 10 wt% (Fig. 3). Given that the variations in density with MgF₂ percentage depend on the variations in the decomposition rate of HA, the cause of the decrease in the density of these specimens can be attributed to the increase in HA decomposition. However, H₂O is also produced by the replacement of F⁻ with OH⁻ (reaction 3-4). But this replacement occurs at lower temperatures. Thus, the H₂O produced in this reaction vaporizes and discharges from the powder mixture and leads to the fluorapatite (Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆F₂) formation [10].

By increasing the sintering temperature from 900 to 1100 °C, the density increases. The reason for this is that as the sintering temperature increases, the surface melting of the powder particles increases, which leads to higher density of the material [50]. It should be noted that although the increase in sintering temperature facilitates sintering due to improved surface melting and allowing more densification during sintering, this increase in temperature also facilitates phase decomposition of HA and leads to a higher rate of HA decomposition. According to above-mentioned points, HA decomposition has a negative effect on the density and properties of HA-containing materials. Therefore, a temperature should be chosen for sintering at which the density is not reduced. It was observed that by increasing the temperature from 900 °C to 1100 °C, although the rate of HA decomposition increased (Fig. 3), the condensation is also increased. It can be implied that with increasing temperature, the improvement of sintering has been dominant over the increase in the decomposition rate and resulting in higher density. Increasing the density of HA specimens due to increment of sintering temperature has also been reported by Z. Evis et al. [10].

Fig. 6. SEM images of sintered specimens at 1100 °C: (a) 0 wt.% MgF₂; b) 5 wt.% MgF₂; c) 7.5 wt.% MgF₂; d) 10 wt.% MgF₂.

Fig. 8. Fracture toughness variations as a function of MgF₂ content at different temperatures.

3.3. Microstructure

SEM images of the specimens at different temperatures are presented in Figs. 4-6. Accordingly, the amount of porosity in the specimens decreased with increasing MgF₂ and the pores became smaller. As stated, the decomposition of HA to TCP decreases with increasing MgF₂ and thus the H₂O produced by this phase decomposition also decreases. This reduces the porosity of the sintered specimens, that has been reported by other researchers [9, 10]. In fact, SEM images confirm the trend obtained for density variations.

According to Figs. 4-6, the increase in sintering temperature leads to a decrease in porosity in the structure. The reason is that sintering process improves with increasing temperature. Comparing the figures, it can be said that more surface melting at sintering temperatures of 1000 °C and 1100 °C is occurred compared to 900 °C. At temperatures of 1000 °C and 1100 °C, the particles and the grains are more difficult to separate and are more interconnected. However, it should be considered that in the specimens that have been sintered at higher temperatures (1000 °C and 1100 °C), porosities are relatively coarser. These are due to the higher phase decomposition of HA at these temperatures. As mentioned, increasing the temperature on one hand increases the phase decomposition and on the other hand, allows for higher densities to facilitate sintering. Although sintering improvement was dominant at this temperature range and resulted in a decrease in the overall porosity as well as increasing the density, due to more H₂O production during the HA decomposition, the size of porosities in the MgF₂-free specimens was larger than that of 900 °C. However, as can be seen in Fig. 4 to 6, this did not occur at higher MgF₂ percentages. Generally, these results

confirm the trend for density variations in the specimens and other researches [51, 52].

3.4. Hardness and Fracture Toughness

As stated, the most important reason for the use of additives such as MgF_2 in HA materials is their effect on improving the mechanical properties of HA, which improves its usability in fields requiring mechanical load bearings. Both hardness and fracture toughness are two important mechanical properties that should be studied. The variation of micro-hardness as a function of MgF_2 percentage is shown in Fig. 7.

The fracture toughness of the specimens was calculated using Eq. 3 and its variation in terms of MgF_2 content is shown in Fig. 8. The obtained results of the hardness and fracture toughness show that by the addition of MgF_2 to HA, the hardness and fracture toughness increase. The fracture toughness of MgF_2 -free HA sample is approximately $1.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, while by addition of MgF_2 it was increased to $2.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is significantly high.

The higher the amount of MgF_2 , the greater the hardness and fracture toughness, especially at 7.5% and 10 wt. %. The reason for this increase can be attributed to the improvement in the density of the specimen by increasing the amount of MgF_2 . The higher density or the lower porosity leads to the higher structural connection and the greater resistance to mechanical loading. Fracture toughness indicates the material resistance to the formation and growth of cracks. When there is a greater potential for crack growth in the material, less fracture toughness or energy absorption is obtained in the sample before fracture. Therefore, the presence of porosity in the material results in reduced fracture toughness.

Generally, the hardness and fracture toughness of HA specimens are depended on the density and porosity. Higher density due to lower phase decomposition of HA or improving the sintering by optimizing the effective parameters such as temperature is achieved. The dependence of hardness and fracture toughness on porosity has also been reported by other researchers [9, 10, 13].

4. Conclusions

In the present study, MgF_2 with values of 5, 7.5 and 10 wt % was added to HA. The powders were milled and sintered at various temperatures for one hour after cold pressing. The most important results of this study are as follows:

1. The addition of MgF_2 , due to the substitution of F^- with OH^- in the structure of HA, resulted in the formation of a more stable fluorapatite phase, thus reducing the phase decomposition of HA to TCP.
2. Increasing the amount of MgF_2 led to lower phase decomposition resulted in an increase in density, and consequently an increase in hardness and fracture toughness.
3. Increasing the sintering temperature resulted in an increase in the amount of HA phase decomposition, while the structure became denser i.e. better mechanical properties.
4. The best amount of MgF_2 to reduce the phase decomposition and achieve the desired density and properties, depends on the sintering temperature. The optimum amount of MgF_2 is 10 wt% for the temperature of 1100°C and 7.5 wt% for the temperatures of 900°C and 1000°C .
5. Fracture toughness values increased from $1.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ for pure sintered HA to $2.3 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, respectively.
6. Maximum density, hardness and fracture toughness were obtained for sintering temperature of 1100°C at 10 wt.% MgF_2 .

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Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflicts of interest in this paper.

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